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OUTSOURCING AS SEEN FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

This article analyzes outsourcing from a knowledge-based perspective. We investigate how knowledge as an organizational resource and the capabilities to manage this knowledge affect the benefits of outsourcing. Our results indicate that the nature of the knowledge of the outsourced activity affects the success of outsourcing. We also analyze the way in which collaborative knowhow (as a knowledge resource) and learning capability (as an organizational capability) affect outsourcing benefits. We then test the validity of this hypothesis by surveying organizations from the service sector. The results of the empirical study provide strong support for our assertion that knowledge management affects the results of outsourcing decisions.

Keywords

Outsourcing; Service Sector; Resource-Based View; Knowledge-Based View; Learning

1. Introduction

In recent years outsourcing has become one of the most widely used management strategies (Giunipero, Hooker, Joseph-Matthews, Yoon and Brudvig 2008), particularly in the service sector (Li and Choi 2009; Tate, Ellram, Bals and Hartmann 2009). In spite of its increasing use, its impact on company results is far from clear. Whereas some studies have found positive results in terms of variables such as efficiency, cost savings or access to new technologies (Powell, Koput and Smith-Doerr 1996; Heshmati 2003), others have reached the opposite conclusion (Jiang, Frazier and Prater 2006; Broedner, Kinkel and Lay 2009).

In this article we analyze the results of outsourcing from the perspective of the resource-based view (RBV) (Wernerfelt 1984; Barney 1991) and more specifically, the knowledge-based view of the firm, which other researchers have found to be a useful approach for the study of outsourcing strategies (Balakrishnan, Mohan and Seshadri

2008), although only a limited number of empirical studies have so far been performed to analyze its importance (Weigelt 2009). This approach views the company as a store of knowledge, and states that the characteristics that distinguish one company from the next, and therefore explain why some companies perform better than others, are the knowledge available to them and their ability to manage this knowledge effectively (Conner and Prahalad 1996). We therefore decided to study the way in which knowledge, considered as a resource of the company, affects performance. However, an analysis focused exclusively on the knowledge base of a company viewed as one of its resources would not provide a complete picture, as it is perhaps even more important to study what the company does with these resources, or in other words its capabilities (Barney 2001). To this end, this article focuses on learning capability, as this is a core process in the knowledge-based view of the company (Grant 1996).

Within the knowledge-based view, the questions we propose to tackle in our research are therefore as follows:

- Do the particular characteristics of the knowledge of the outsourced activity affect the benefits expected to be gained from outsourcing?
- Can the available knowledge and the capabilities to manage it influence the benefits of outsourcing?

By this means we hope to shed some light on previous contradictory findings on the results of outsourcing. One of the main contributions of our study is to find contingent factors that explain the disparities between the results of previous studies of the benefits of outsourcing using the theoretical approach of the knowledge-based view of the company. Given that the knowledge-based view is of fundamental importance for studying the reasons why some companies are more profitable than others (Grant 1996), there are still many interesting questions to answer regarding its importance in explaining the competitive advantages arising from relationships with suppliers (Dyer and Nobeoka 2000). A second contribution is that to achieve this, we use variables that are related to both the resources and the capabilities of the company, which we analyze within the same model.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. We begin with a review of the main theoretical contributions, which is followed by the presentation of the hypotheses and the study's model. Afterwards, we present the methodology, including the selection of the sample and the measurement of the constructs, and we finish by presenting the main results, their discussion and the most important conclusions reached.

2. Literature review

2.1. The RBV and the Knowledge-Based View of the Firm

The RBV is based on the idea that organizations possess a series of resources that enable them, on the one hand, to obtain sustainable competitive advantages and, on the other, to achieve greater long-term performance (Penrose 1959; Wernerfelt 1984; Barney 1986, 1991; Grant 1991; Ray, Barney and Muhanna 2004). This theory would explain why there are substantial differences in performance between organizations that belong to the same industry sector (Mahoney and Pandian 1992; Kor and Mahoney 2004). The conventional

approach considers the general sources of competitive advantage, namely advantages in cost and differentiation (Porter 1985). However, the RBV focuses on the resources and capabilities that form the basis of these advantages. This theory should not be considered an instrument or technique of internal analysis but rather an integrative conceptual framework for the analysis, formulation and implementation of business strategies (Ireland and Hitt 2005). In fact, this theory has been used before to analyze the repercussions of production and supply decisions such as lean production (Lewis 2000; Shah and Ward 2003) or outsourcing (Weigelt 2009).

In providing more in-depth examination of how resources and capabilities are identified, some authors speak of resources in a very general sense, making no distinction between assets and capabilities (Hall 1993; Barney 2001). Others distinguish two levels of analysis, the first referring to the individual resources or assets and the second to the collective capabilities, competencies, or abilities of the organization that enable it to perform a business activity successfully by combining and coordinating the individual resources available. Thus, the firm's resources and capabilities can be understood as the set of elements, factors, assets, abilities and attributes that the firm possesses or controls and that enable it to formulate and put into action a competitive strategy (Grant 1996; Sirmon, Hitt and Ireland 2007).

It is not always easy, however, to distinguish between resources and capabilities. Mahoney and Pandian (1992) state that “resources have the character of stock, whereas capabilities are fluid and can be seen as ways of utilizing resources.” The step from possessing individual abilities and resources to obtaining collective capabilities is determined by organizational routines (Helfat and Peteraf 2003). Specific capabilities for very specific tasks are created from individual resources. These capabilities are then integrated into more complex capabilities, and so on. Organizational routines are the link that enables the firm to continue creating this hierarchy from the integration of specific resources and capabilities. We can thus establish relationships between the firm's resources and capabilities and the resulting competitive advantage.

The empirical results of studies by Schmalensee (1983), Henderson and Cockburn (1994), Roos, Edvinsson and Roos (1998), Powell and Dent-Micallef (1997), Spanos and Lioukas (2001), and Powell, Lovallo and Caringal (2006), among others, lead us to a better theoretical framework for studying the sources of sustained competitive advantage and, ultimately, improved performance. When resources are scarce, they become valuable and this leads to temporary competitive advantages. If organizations can protect their main resources from imitation, transfer or substitution, these competitive advantages can become sustainable (Hulland 2004), so confirming the strategic decisions taken by the firm (Parker and Russell 2004).

The framework of the resources and capabilities theory helps us to understand the importance that knowledge has acquired in recent years. The knowledge that an organization uses in performing its tasks can be considered a resource (Grant 1996) which, in view of its characteristics, has become the central axis of the theory of resources and capabilities (Conner and Prahalad 1996). Knowledge, especially tacit knowledge, is scarce, and difficult to transfer and imitate (Winter 1987), which makes it a particularly promising candidate as a resource that meets the conditions for it to be considered a source of competitive advantage. Tacit knowledge can be defined as the noncodifiable accumulation of skills that arise from the learning gained from practice (Reed and

DeFillippi 1990). Tacit knowledge is a highly personal resource in that it cannot be easily passed on or shared. It originates in the action and the specific conduct of individuals when placed in a particular context (Nonaka 1994). The dichotomy between tacit and explicit knowledge can be expressed in terms of the knowledge gained from experience (Johanson and Vahlne 1977), as opposed to articulated knowledge (Senker and Faulkner 1996).

Within the same analytical framework, the processes for managing knowledge can be considered as capabilities that the firm develops to enable it to manage knowledge as a resource. Although different authors identify different numbers of knowledge management processes, the basic processes are knowledge creation or learning, knowledge transfer and knowledge application (Nonaka and Takeuchi 1995; Grant 1996). Thus, the object of knowledge management is not only the management of the stock of knowledge but also the development of the capabilities required for managing this knowledge (Raisinghani and Meade 2005).

2.2. Service Outsourcing and Knowledge Management

Outsourcing occurs when a firm outside the organization performs a process or activity traditionally conducted within the organization (Gilley and Rasheed 2000). Outsourcing involves restructuring the firm's activities in order to stimulate the development of its core business by externalizing less important activities and those that are not a source of competitive advantage (Prahalad and Hamel 1990). There are several different types of outsourcing (Dibbern, Goles, Hirschheim and Jayatilaka 2004). Millar (1994) defines the following four basic types:

- (a) General outsourcing, which covers three alternatives: (a) selective outsourcing, (b) value-added outsourcing or (c) cooperative outsourcing.
- (b) Transitional outsourcing, which involves the process of moving from one technological platform to another.
- (c) Business process outsourcing: a relationship in which a third party supplier performs an entire business function for the client organization.
- (d) Business benefit contracting: This refers to a “contractual agreement that defines the vendor's contribution to the client in terms of specific benefits to the business and defines the payment the customer will make based upon the vendor's ability to deliver those benefits” (Millar 1994, as cited in Dibbern et al. 2004, p. 10).

Willcocks and Lacity (1998) discuss six forms of what they call “emerging sourcing arrangements”: value-added outsourcing— where the strengths of the parties to the outsourcing arrangement are combined so as to enable them to market new products and services; equity holdings— where one party acquires equity in the other; multisourcing— where there is one outsourcing contract but several providers of the service; co-sourcing— where the outsourcing vendors' revenue is linked to the performance of the company that the services are provided to; spin-offs— where the internal IS department is converted into a new company that sells its services to the market; and creative contracting— which includes personalized clauses to satisfy specific customer requirements.

Service outsourcing is defined as a “conscious choice of replacing internal service functions with the use of external agents to perform one or more service activities” (Li

and Choi 2009, p. 28). We should not be deceived by the similar definitions provided for product outsourcing and service outsourcing, as there are important differences between the two (Maltz and Sautter 1995).

The specific characteristics of service outsourcing make knowledge management particularly important in this kind of outsourcing (Blumenberg, Wagner and Beimborn 2009), as the need for greater coordination and a direct relationship with the supplier of the service obliges companies to take more care with knowledge transfers, improve mechanisms for integration with the supplier and encourage the creation of shared knowledge.

In fact, the knowledge-based view has been used in previous research as a basis for analyzing outsourcing in general, as a means of finding answers to the fundamental dilemma of which activities to outsource. Outsourcing has been proposed as the best option for those activities in which there is a lack of knowledge resources or when these resources have little or no relation to the company's core knowledge field (Grant and Baden-Fuller 2004). In addition Weigelt (2009) found that having experience in prior related technology improved outsourcing performance, and if companies had this knowledge it was therefore better for them to outsource. In producing/purchasing decisions, the nature of knowledge is considered to be very important. On this question, Kogut and Zander (1996) stated that when knowledge is tacit, it is better to perform potentially outsourceable activities in-house.

The knowledge-based view has also been used to analyze how the outsourcing relationship should be managed. Researchers have stressed the need to create shared knowledge (Blumenberg et al. 2009), or the need to maintain peripheral knowledge even in activities that have been completely outsourced (Tiwana and Keil 2007).

3. Hypotheses

3.1. Relationship Between the Characteristics of Knowledge and the Benefits of Outsourcing

Researchers have analyzed many different characteristics or aspects of an organization's knowledge (Winter 1987). From a decision-based perspective, the fundamental characteristics that determine the appropriateness of a decision are the accessibility and the quality of the knowledge used to make it (O'Reilly 1982). Accessibility refers to the ease with which knowledge is made available to be used where the firm needs it. Quality refers to the appropriateness of the knowledge available for the decision that must be made. These two characteristics of organizational knowledge are intimately related to the smooth functioning of the networks (both technological and social) that the firm uses to manage knowledge. By technological networks we mean those in which the participants interact primarily by means of the transfer of knowledge and information via technological media such as the Internet. In social networks, personal interaction between the members is necessary. In any case, regardless of which of these two kinds of networks the relationship with the company that provides the outsourcing service is based on, the specific characteristics of the knowledge will be key factors in determining the ease with which this relationship is managed (O'Reilly 1982).

With regard to outsourcing decisions, the more knowledge available and the better the access to it, the lower the uncertainty, which will lead to lower levels of opportunism and thus ensure that better contracts are obtained. The quality of the information available to the firm is therefore a determining factor, and we can assert a direct relationship between the quality of information that the decider possesses and the results of the decision that is made (Porat and Haas 1969; Low and Mohr 2001).

On the other hand, outsourcing is motivated by the growing pressures on managers to remain competitive by using fewer resources or by using current resource levels to obtain ever greater objectives (Insinga and Werle 2000). The strategic vulnerability that outsourcing generates (Quinn and Hilmer 1994) can be decreased to the extent that companies manage their knowledge well (O'Reilly 1982). A company's capability to access knowledge (represented by the quality and accessibility of knowledge that the decider possesses) can mitigate the vulnerability that results from decisions to outsource activities. In view of the above, we can hypothesize that:

H1a: The quality of the firm's knowledge of the outsourced activity is positively related to outsourcing benefits.

H1b: The accessibility of the firm's knowledge of the outsourced activity is positively related to outsourcing benefits.

Most studies have focused on analyzing the characteristics of knowledge that facilitate or inhibit its transfer. In studying the process of knowledge transmission between sender and receiver, it is crucial to analyze the kind of knowledge to be transferred, which can range from the most tacit to the most explicit (Nonaka and Takeuchi 1995). Tacit knowledge is defined as personal knowledge associated with a specific context, and thus is difficult to express formally, while explicit knowledge permits formal and systematic transfer. Thus, tacit knowledge is defined as knowledge that cannot be expressed verbally or symbolically, whereas explicit knowledge is represented in written or symbolic form (Lee 2001). In the specific case of outsourcing, the degree of tacitness of the knowledge required to perform and to manage the outsourced activity affects the potential benefits to be gained from outsourcing.

If knowledge of the outsourced activity is tacit, it makes the outsourcing relationship more difficult to manage and requires greater interaction between the parties (Grant 1996). This means that the coordination mechanisms are more costly in terms of the resources consumed, and therefore the potential benefits to be achieved from outsourcing must be weighed against the costs involved in managing the process.

Furthermore, the success of outsourcing is influenced by the effectiveness of the relationship established between the partners. We propose a hypothesis concerning the relation between the degree of knowledge transmission based on the tacitness of the knowledge and the benefits expected from the outsourcing of a specific activity. In this hypothesis, tacitness refers to a measure of knowledge transfer ranging from more to less tacit. However, the process of knowledge transfer between parties can be sticky, or difficult to achieve (Szulanski 1996). This enables us to assert that when knowledge is tacit, more problems arise during its transfer (Molina, Montes and Fuentes 2004), thus making it more difficult for companies to control their outsourcing relationships. Therefore:

H1c: The tacitness of the knowledge required to manage the outsourcing relationship is negatively related to outsourcing benefits.

3.2. Relationship Between Organizational Learning Capability and the Benefits of Outsourcing

An organization that learns is one that develops the abilities necessary for creating, acquiring and transferring knowledge in a way that changes its behavior to reflect the new knowledge acquired (Garvin 1993). The structure of this kind of organization is designed to make this learning process truly effective (Slater and Narver 1995). Because of its multidimensional character, organizational learning will include many subprocesses related to the acquisition and dissemination of the information available, including the process of joint interpretation of this information (Sinkula 1994). Given this conceptual complexity, organizational learning includes different disciplines, such as systems thinking, personal mastery, mental models, shared vision and learning teams (Senge 1990).

The organizational learning capability is conceptualized by the different definitions of organizational learning (see among others Normann 1985; Senge 1990; Day 1991, 1994; McKee 1992; Wick and Leon 1993; Sinkula 1994) in conjunction with the different cognitive subprocesses and levels of this learning, all elements that belong to a multidimensional construct like the one discussed here (Hult and Ferrell 1997). But if we look beyond its conceptual complexity, learning capability becomes a determining factor for success when the firm competes in global markets, where the absence of this capability can create significant difficulties for the firm (Prahalad and Hamel 1990; Senge 1990; Nonaka and Takeuchi 1995).

Prior studies demonstrate that it is important for firms to know how to manage their relationships with external partners in terms of the knowledge they should acquire if they do not want short-term outsourcing benefits to become long-term strategic problems (Brusoni, Prencipe and Pavitt 2001). Thus, the firm should not only maintain the capability to gain the knowledge required for its current activities, but also must recognize that learning capability is a key factor in avoiding the uncertainties arising from the future development of the knowledge bases on which the firm's management decisions are based.

The learning capability is also related to the potential benefits of outsourcing insofar as it allows the company to access the knowledge of its partner. One of the main benefits of outsourcing is the opportunity it provides to access new technologies (Weigelt 2009). However, in order for the company to be able to take advantage of this opportunity, it must have sufficient learning capability to enable it to adapt its structures and processes to the requirements of this new technology.

Likewise, organizational learning capability can reduce the strategic vulnerability created by outsourcing.

H2: Organizational learning is positively related to outsourcing benefits.

3.3. The Relationship Between Know-How in Collaborative Relationships and the Benefits of Outsourcing

Tacit knowledge is intangible and difficult to formalize, but is “visible” in action, and emanates from two sources, a social source (communities of practice) and a cognitive source (know-how) (Simmers 2004). Know-how is the set of abilities developed over time, understood as transcending experience to enable the individual to adjust and improve this experience over time (Simmers 2004). But know-how can be lost during the process of knowledge transfer in relationships with external partners (Galbraith 1990). This risk is so high that some companies draw up rules concerning such knowledge transfers (Spekman, Spear and Kamauff 2002), including explicit rules on the handling of documents and their dissemination.

It is thus evident that know-how in collaborative relationships is essential in managing outsourcing. Prior experience of these relationships will prevent the risks mentioned above and help the firm obtain benefits from joint operations with other firms (Powell et al. 1996). This is particularly true in certain alliances that are established deliberately to enable firms to learn from their partner's abilities. The main objective of such alliances is to acquire as much as possible of the know-how in which their partner specializes (Grant and Baden-Fuller 2004).

A full evaluation of the benefits derived from the learning acquired in collaborative relationships requires a study of the consequences of these benefits from a long-term perspective. Such a study must analyze the concept of know-how based on a time frame to be considered from the ex ante, during, and ex post perspectives. In addition, firms experienced in maintaining successful strategic alliances will be able to develop the collaborative know-how that enables them to achieve their maximum potential, thereby enabling us to hypothesize that:

H3: Collaborative know-how enhances outsourcing benefits.

Finally, Figure 1 shows the model resulting from considering the different hypotheses together. It demonstrates the way in which the availability and the characteristics of knowledge, learning capability and collaborative know-how are all proposed as variables that influence the degree of the benefits obtained from outsourcing.

4. Methods

4.1. *Sample and data*

Our study uses survey research to test the proposed hypotheses. The population studied is made up of firms in the service sector. We restricted our target group to firms located in Spain with over 20 employees. The database we used was the DICODI 2005–06 directory, which provides information about the largest 50,000 Spanish corporations. From this number, 12,587 firms belong to the service sector and have more than 20 employees. The analysis of the data gathered in the sample was performed with the statistical software SPSS 15.0 and EQS 6.1. A sample of 1,000 firms was chosen at random and each was asked to take part in the research. Eight questionnaires were returned due to mistakes in the address, and these were not replaced by other companies. The data were collected between November 2006 and April 2007. Given the difficulty of obtaining responses when asking questions about strategic aspects, we took special care when preparing the questionnaire, so as to maximize the response rate. To this end, we began by pretesting the questionnaire by carrying out a series of in-depth interviews with CEOs from firms in the sample group. The first batch of questionnaires was then sent out by post, and a total of 112 valid replies were received. Nonrespondents (880 firms) were then sent a new questionnaire about 2 months after the initial mailing. By the end of this process we had obtained a total of 204 valid questionnaires, giving a response rate of 20.6 percent. This response rate is similar to that achieved in previous studies investigating similar subjects (Kaufmann and Carter 2006; Kroes and Ghosh 2010). The questionnaire was addressed to CEOs, because of the wide range of departments from which they receive information, and because of their ability to evaluate the variables under analysis in the study (Baer and Frese 2003).

We also analyzed the possible bias caused by nonrespondent firms. The aforementioned database provides secondary information on the number of employees and the turnover, both for firms in the sample and for nonrespondents. We used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to check that the size of the company was not an issue and no significant differences were found in either the number of employees ($p=0.658$) or the turnover ($p=0.785$). These results suggest that the respondent firms do not obviously differ from the nonrespondent group.

4.2. *Measures*

Quality and Accessibility of Knowledge. To measure the variables, we used a seven-point Likert scale based on the scale developed by O'Reilly (1982). The quality and the accessibility of the knowledge available are crucial factors that determine the capability of the person that makes decisions in the firm to use this knowledge effectively. They are crucial because there is inherent ambiguity in the knowledge available and tremendous pressure on managers to obtain better results from the decisions they make. The quality of knowledge therefore has a direct effect on the consequences of these decisions.

We carried out an exploratory factor analysis to find out if there were really two constructs or if all the items loaded on a single factor, which would imply that the CEOs who replied had not distinguished between the two concepts of quality and accessibility. The results of this analysis can be seen in Table I, where we can see that there are two factors with eigenvalues >1 , which correspond to a large extent, with the initial scales for quality and accessibility of knowledge proposed by O'Reilly (1982). The analysis also shows that items QUA6, QUA7 and ACC2 do not load on the factor in which they theoretically should (see Table I). We then studied whether all the items could be used by analyzing the item–total correlation. According to Hair, Anderson, Tatham and Black (2001) this must be >0.5 . This analysis revealed that items QUA2 on the quality scale and ACC2 on the accessibility scale did not meet this condition and we therefore removed them from the scales. On the accessibility scale, none of the items met this condition, so we decided not to use this scale. In the scale for knowledge quality, the Cronbach α was 0.824, indicating the scale's internal consistency. The composite reliability and extracted variance indicators can be seen in Table IV.

Table I. Exploratory Factor Analysis and Item–Total Correlation of the Quality and Accessibility of Knowledge

Items	Quality	Accessibility	Item–Total Correlation	
			Quality	Accessibility
QUA1	0.861		0.759	
QUA2	0.610		0.484	
QUA3	0.801		0.691	
QUA4	0.807		0.695	
QUA5	0.824		0.705	
QUA6		0.705		0.373
QUA7		0.657		0.349
ACC1		0.791		0.392
ACC2	0.600		0.470	

Items	Quality	Accessibility	Item–Total Correlation	
			Quality	Accessibility
ACC3		0.740		0.346
Common variance accounted for (%)	36.825	27.235		

Table IV. Factor Loadings and Reliability Analysis

Construct/ Items	Mean	SD	Initial Model	R^2	Final Model	R^2	Composite Reliability	Variance Extracted
			Factor Loading (t- Values)		Factor Loading (t- Values)			
<i>Quality knowledge</i>							0.797	0.496
QUA1	4.254	1.567			0.846 (13.959)	0.714		
QUA2			0.836 (11.54)	0.315				
QUA3	4.673	1.577			0.744 (11.590)	0.547		
QUA4	4.309	1.609			0.753 (11.923)	0.609		
QUA5	4.353	1.558			0.778 (12.526)	0.612		
<i>Tacit knowledge</i>							0.756	0.615
TAC1			0.778 (3.87)	0.215				
TAC2			0.696 (3.35)	0.195				

Construct/ Items	Mean	SD	Initial Model Factor Loading (t- Values)	R ²	Final Model Factor Loading (t- Values)	R ²	Composite Reliability	Variance Extracted
TAC3	4.441	1.545			0.915 (3.250)	0.521		
TAC4	4.569	1.469			0.855 (3.224)	0.495		
<i>Learning capability</i>							0.870	0.625
LER1	4.843	1.620			0.871 (17.422)	0.501		
LER2	4.828	1.605			0.926 (18.950)	0.485		
LER3	4.681	1.673			0.874 (17.053)	0.475		
LER4	4.872	1.709			0.858 (16.503)	0.489		
<i>Collaborator know-how</i>								
<i>Ex-Ante</i>							0.805	0.509
KH1	5.157	1.315			0.834 (14.338)	0.695		
KH2	5.122	1.372			0.808 (13.619)	0.654		
KH3	5.250	1.347			0.901 (15.992)	0.713		
KH4	5.206	1.461			0.823 (13.995)	0.678		
<i>During</i>							0.853	0.539
KH8	4.951	1.399			0.851 (8.430)	0.627		

Construct/ Items	Mean	SD	Initial Model Factor Loading (t- Values)	R ²	Final Model Factor Loading (t- Values)	R ²	Composite Reliability	Variance Extracted
KH9	4.843	1.409			0.853 (8.439)	0.630		
KH11	4.838	1.455			0.836 (8.341)	0.598		
KH12	4.877	1.521			0.776 (7.999)	0.499		
KH13	4.907	1.402			0.837 (8.345)	0.599		
<i>Ex-post</i>							0.766	0.522
KH14	4.613	1.463			0.756 (11.824)	0.572		
KH15	4.049	1.488			0.792 (12.477)	0.628		
KH16	4.505	1.500			0.879 (12.125)	0.6033		
<i>Benefits of outsourcing</i>								
<i>Business benefits</i>							0.808	0.514
BUSB1			0.726 (8.543)	0.335				
BUSB2			0.744 (7.987)	0.253				
BUSB3	5.059	1.565			0.720 (8.264)	0.531		
BUSB4			0.693 (8.235)	0.278				
BUSB5	4.789	1.702			0.689 (7.562)	0.543		

Construct/ Items	Mean	SD	Initial Model Factor Loading (t- Values)	R ²	Final Model Factor Loading (t- Values)	R ²	Composite Reliability	Variance Extracted
BUSB6	5.118	1.514			0.759 (8.197)	0.528		
BUSB7	4.882	1.599			0.823 (8.772)	0.552		
<i>Organizational benefits</i>							0.811	0.518
ORGB1			0.814 (10.678)	0.415				
ORGB2	4.657	1.625			0.762 (12.300)	0.571		
ORGB3	4.691	1.666			0.857 (13.278)	0.614		
ORGB4			0.693 (11.865)	0.218				
ORGB5	4.637	1.540			0.815 (13.562)	0.654		
ORGB6	4.461	1.519			0.868 (13.961)	0.661		
ORGB7			0.674 (10.879)	0.175				
ORGB8			0.813 (11.907)	0.345				

$\chi^2=1619.137$, $df=830$; GFI=0.917; RMSEA=0.068; RMR=0.047; AGFI=0.901; NFI=0.947; NNFI=0.958; CFI=0.930; $\chi^2/df=1.951$.

^aAll of the factor loadings are significant for a level of $p<0.01$.

Tacitness of Knowledge. We used the scale for analyzing tacitness proposed by Molina et al. (2004). These authors took the most important characteristics of the tacitness of knowledge set out in Kogut and Zander (1996), and used a single scale to analyze the degree of tacitness of knowledge. This scale has four items measured by a Likert scale from 1 to 7 from “Totally disagree” to “Totally agree.”

Learning Capability. This scale is made up of four items and is based on the scale used by Kale, Singh and Perlmutter (2000) with the modifications made by García-Morales, Lloréns-Montes and Verdú-Jover (2007) for the measurement of the company's learning capability. In this article the scale was used to measure the capability of the company to acquire new knowledge and improve the capabilities of the company through learning. The scale ranges from 1=“Totally disagree” to 7=“Totally agree.”

Know-How in Collaborative Relationships. Using the scale developed by Simonin (1999), we attempted to establish a relationship between prior experience in collaborative relationships and success in current relationships. Experience in these kinds of relationships is essential for managing a portfolio of different allies, as it helps companies benefit from the resulting relationships (Powell, Koput and Smith-Doerr 1996). In fact, lack of prior collaborative experience is in some cases the main source of problems in alliances and thus the main cause of their failure (Lei and Slocum 1992). Past experience promotes the emergence of a distinctive know-how that enables firms to obtain greater benefits from subsequent alliances (Simonin 1997). Understanding the transfer mechanisms and processes underlying collaborative relationships encourages knowledge absorption. We therefore asked those participating in the survey to quantify on a seven-point Likert scale (1=slight development of know-how, 7=great development of know-how) the degree to which their knowledge of the different aspects of these relationships had developed as a result of previous collaborative experience.

In order to check the dimensionality of the scale, we subjected it to exploratory factor analysis (Table II). Four factors had an eigenvalue greater than one. These four factors were then subjected to a validity analysis using the item-total correlation. This analysis showed that item KH9, and one of the dimensions (factor 4) did not comply with the minimum conditions (Hair et al. 2001). These were therefore both eliminated. We then analyzed which items loaded on each factor. After this analysis we gave names to each of the dimensions of the collaborative know-how as factors of the same prior to (EX-ANTE), during (DURING) and after (EX-POST) the collaborative relationship. All of these dimensions met the condition of having a Cronbach's Alpha above the recommended levels (Hair et al. 2001) (EX-ANTE α =0.905, DURING α =0.917, EX-POST α =0.849). The same applies for their composite reliability and variance extracted values (Table IV).

Table II. Exploratory Factor Analysis and Item–Total Correlation for Collaborative Know-How

Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Item–Total Correlation			
	Ex-ante	During	Ex-Post		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
KH1	0.848				0.812			
KH2	0.822				0.758			

Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Item–Total Correlation			
	Ex-ante	During	Ex-Post		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
KH3	0.754				0.841			
KH4	0.632				0.743			
KH5		0.747				0.348		
KH6		0.783				0.315		
KH7		0.628				0.356		
KH8		0.653				0.402		
KH9		0.680				0.409		
KH10			0.498				0.380	
KH11		0.584				0.757		
KH12		0.764				0.806		
KH13		0.770				0.803		
KH14			0.725				0.681	
KH15			0.791				0.827	
KH16			0.776				0.716	
KH17				0.727				0.288
KH18				0.712				0.295

Items	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Item–Total Correlation			
	Ex-ante	During	Ex-Post		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
KH19				0.840				0.251
KH20				0.774				0.210
Common variance accounted for (%)	20.041	20.157	18.456	10.664				

In bold: values under the minimum value 0.400. Items needs values >0.400 (Hair et al. 2001).

For our analysis we used these three dimensions of collaborative know-how, however, as we were particularly interested in analyzing their combined effect. In the causal analysis we grouped them together in a second-order construct (collaborative know-how), which is formed by three first-order constructs (know-how prior, know-how during, and know-how after).

Benefits of Outsourcing. Ehie (2001) and Kremic, Tukel and Rom (2006) proposed that outsourcing contributed to the development of essential capabilities and established a series of potential benefits that arose from outsourcing strategies. Based on their propositions, we developed scale items using a seven-point, strongly disagree-strongly agree Likert scale.

The results obtained from analyzing this scale revealed two main components, business and organizational benefits, and showed that the study of their unidimensionality was positive (Table III). Item-total correlation was used to study validity. BUS8 and BUS9 items were eliminated as they don't approach the minimum acceptability level. Regarding the scale's internal consistency, we obtained a value of $\alpha=0.877$ for business benefits and $\alpha=0.756$ for organizational benefits, which shows that these scales are an appropriate measurement instrument for the purposes for which they were designed.

Table III. Exploratory Factor Analysis and Item–Total Correlation for Outsourcing Benefits

Items	Business Benefits	Organizational Benefits	Item–Total Correlation	
			Business Benefits	Organizational Benefits
BUSB1	0.781		0.526	
BUSB2	0.802		0.599	
BUSB3	0.678		0.503	
BUSB4	0.577		0.486	
BUSB5	0.751		0.529	
BUSB6	0.719		0.523	
BUSB7	0.652		0.578	
BUSB8	0.476		0.325	
BUSB9	0.486		0.287	
ORGB1		0.637		0.678
ORGB2		0.759		0.527
ORGB3		0.849		0.632
ORGB4		0.693		0.651
ORGB5		0.802		0.753
ORGB6		0.813		0.672
ORGB7		0.593		0.745

Items	Business Benefits	Organizational Benefits	Item–Total Correlation	
			Business Benefits	Organizational Benefits
ORGB8	0.492	0.483	0.426	
ORGB9		0.412	0.301	
Common variance accounted for (%)	29.864	32.988		

In bold: values under the minimum value 0.400. Items needs values >0.400 (Hair et al. 2001).

After analyzing each scale individually to ensure unidimensionality and reliability, we then studied the measurement model as a whole. For this purpose, we performed a confirmatory factor analysis, as a result of which some of the items had to be eliminated, as they did not comply with the condition of having an individual reliability of greater than 0.4 (Hair et al. 2001). This information is shown in Table IV. This table includes the values for composite reliability and variance extracted for each scale. It is clear that these values fall within the margins considered as acceptable. The discriminant validity of the scales was also analyzed. Here, for each pair of constructs, the correlation between them was forced to one (Wilcox, Howell and Breivik 2008). We then checked the loss of fit resulting from this modification. A statistically significant loss would provide evidence of the discriminant validity of the scales. All results were significant.

5. Results and findings

The results of the structural analysis are shown in Figure 2. In evaluating the structural model, we examined the goodness-of-fit index (GFI), adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), root mean square residual (RMR), normed fit index (NFI), nonnormed fit index (NNFI) and comparative fit index (CFI). All of these indicators suggest an appropriate fit between the structural model and the data (GFI=0.917, AGFI=0.901, RMSEA=0.068, RMR=0.047, NFI=0.947, NNFI=0.958, CFI=0.930).

Figure 2. Results of the Structural Analysis

The results of the analysis are consistent with the hypotheses proposed. These results agree with the general study hypothesis that the variables of knowledge management have a positive influence on the benefits obtained from outsourcing.

6. Discussion

The results of the empirical study support all the hypotheses put forward in this study, with the exception of Hypothesis 1b, which relates the accessibility of knowledge and outsourcing benefits, and which we were unable to test due to problems with the reliability of the measurement scale we used. Our results therefore confirm that there is a positive relationship between the quality of knowledge and outsourcing benefits (H1a; $\beta=0.13$; $p>0.001$), and a negative relationship between the tacitness of knowledge and outsourcing benefits (H1c; $\beta=0.11$; $p>0.001$). These results hold several implications. First and in direct relation to the questions posed in this article, the results reveal that the nature of the knowledge of the outsourced activity affects its success. This means that the quality of knowledge involved is an important contingent variable in explaining why some outsourcing decisions have more positive results than others (Jiang and Quershi 2006). In this respect, our results indicate that the company must maintain a certain quality of knowledge about the outsourced activity, even though it is no longer performed internally. These results agree with the theoretical discussion on this question presented by Brusoni et al. (2001), so adding support to our proposition.

These results also contribute to the field of study referred to as the theory of the firm. This area of research seeks to address fundamental questions such as the reasons why firms exist or where they set their boundaries (Williamson 2008). There is some controversy in this field regarding the importance of the degree of tacitness of knowledge (Kogut and

Zander 1992; Love 1995). Some authors contend that when knowledge is difficult to transfer, as is the case of tacit knowledge, companies perform the associated task better than markets. The results of our work support this view, in that the more tacit the knowledge, the fewer the benefits that can be obtained from outsourcing. These findings suggest that it may be preferable to perform such activities in-house. This is important both for the definition of the boundaries of the company and indeed for its very existence, as the firm's existence is justified by the fact that the mechanisms of the company can manage tacit knowledge more effectively than market agreements.

In addition, our results confirm the validity of the hypotheses concerning the positive effect of collaborative know-how (H2; $\beta=0.26$; $p>0.001$) and learning capability (H3; $\beta=0.23$; $p>0.01$) on the benefits of outsourcing. These results have several interesting implications. First, they allow us to contribute to the literature on outsourcing by adding both collaborative know-how and learning capability as contingent factors that affect the success or the benefits obtained from outsourcing. This means that from a knowledge-based perspective, not only is it important to analyze the nature of the knowledge of the outsourced activity, but we must also consider the aforementioned contingent factors to allow us to evaluate potential benefits of outsourcing processes, a fact which complicates the study of these processes.

Second, and with regard to the nature of the collaborative know-how, we should point out that this not only increases with experience in outsourcing processes, but also in general with the experience acquired by the company in the management of the network of relations with partners and suppliers. This means that outsourcing benefits will be affected by the general strategy of relationships with suppliers and by the capability of the company to gain the necessary experience to manage it effectively. This suggests that the study of outsourcing processes should be performed within the broader framework of company supply chain management, and not as an isolated process, if we wish to analyze its consequences for the company (Hunt and Davis 2008).

The results are equally interesting for researchers in knowledge management. They show the value of the stock of knowledge as a resource, and of learning capability not only as a direct source for generating competitive advantages, but also as an integral part of more complex competences and capabilities, such as the capability to manage outsourcing relations. This enables us to value the firm's knowledge-based resources and capabilities even more highly.

Our results therefore support the view that it is essential to study the complementarities between the firm's resources and capabilities in order to determine their true value. It is not enough to study resources and capabilities in isolation. They have to be studied within their organizational context, where they acquire their true value when used together to perform organizational tasks.

6.1. Limitations of the Research

Although we have demonstrated important relationships between the variables in this study, the results must be interpreted with some caution. First, our information depends on the perception of a single member of the firm, and second we have only studied firms in the service sector.

As this study is a cross-sectional or static analysis, we cannot capture the dynamic nature of the specific factors of the relationship between the variables that influence the benefits of outsourcing. This means that, although the relationships are significant, we have not shown that the variables we studied are the strongest determinants. Other factors not included in the present study may also be influential.

Another important limitation is the lack of reliability and validity of the scale for measuring the accessibility of knowledge, which prevented us from analyzing Hypothesis 1b.

Although the research has limitations, the empirical study performed merits attention because of the diversity of the data used and the reasonableness of their interpretation with respect to the hypotheses proposed. As a whole, our study advances the process of articulating the relationship between outsourcing and the knowledge management variables that influence it.

6.2. Implications for Future Research and Practice

As to future lines of research, it would first be very interesting to study the degree of complementarity and the learning capability of the service provider. It would also be interesting to determine whether a greater or lesser prior level of outsourcing generates some kind of advantage similar to that found with the set of preceding collaborative relationships included in collaborative know-how. In addition, we have only established relationships between quality of knowledge and benefits of outsourcing and were unable to establish a relationship between outsourcing benefits and the accessibility of knowledge or other knowledge characteristics. There are more dimensions of knowledge management that have not been analyzed and about which important conclusions can be drawn, as is the case with use or intensity of knowledge.

As to the model, we have only considered the benefits of outsourcing. In the future, we could also consider the drawbacks, such as externalities arising from offshoring, in particular those relating to its impact on the environment. Finally, we are analyzing outsourcing from a general perspective of service operations. The same study could be performed for a more specific kind of outsourcing (ICTs, logistics, etc.).

Appendix

Items Measuring Quality and Accessibility of Information Sources

Quality

QUA1 — When using information from the following sources, how accurate would you say it usually is?

QUA2 — When using information from these sources it may be necessary to go back and check on the accuracy. How often does this occur on the average?

QUA3 — Sometimes the information we get may get right to the heart of the problem we are facing. Other times the information may not be very specific to our needs. In general, how relevant is the information from the sources?

QUA4 — At times we must gather a lot of information which is not very relevant in order to get enough to be able to make a good decision. Other times we need only a small amount because the information is very specific and allows us to make a decision. How specific is the information from the following?

QUA5 — At times we may be unsure whether to believe in the information we receive from a particular source because it may be unreliable. How often is this the case for the information you obtain from?

QUA6 — Some information may be exactly what we require. How often is this the case for information obtained from the following sources?

QUA7 — To be useful, information must often be available when we need it, not at some later time. How timely would you estimate information to be from the following?

Accessibility

ACC1 — Sometimes information may exist which we know about which would be helpful in decision making, but is not readily available because of the time, expense, or difficulty in obtaining it. In general, how often is this the case with the following?

ACC2 — How accessible or easy to get at is information contained in the following sources?

ACC3 — How difficult is it, on the average, to get information from the following sources?

Source: Adapted from O'Reilly (1982).

Items Measuring Tacitness of Knowledge

Tacitness

TAC1 — The manuals and written procedures contain all the information required to perform the company's main processes and practices.

TAC2 — New employees can learn most of the useful knowledge/skills without having to go through a long period of adaptation to their job.

TAC3 — The association between actions and results of your company's processes and practices are easily understandable for a competitor company.

TAC4 — The competition can understand the process of creation of products and services by using and analyzing them.

Source: Molina et al. (2004).

Items Measuring Learning Capability

Learning capability

LER1 — The organization has learned or acquired a lot of new and important knowledge over the last three years.

LER2 — Members of the organization have learned or acquired some critical capabilities or skills in the last three years.

LER3 — The improvement of the organization has been influenced by the new knowledge acquired by the company in the last three years.

LER4 — Our company is an organization that learns.

Source: García-Morales et al. (2007).

Items Measuring Know-How in Collaborative Relationships

Collaborative know-how

KH1 — partner identification

- KH2 — partner selection
- KH3 — negotiations
- KH4 — legal aspects
- KH5 — understanding strategic implications of collaborating
- KH6 — technological assessment
- KH7 — estimating asset values and future cash flows
- KH8 — tax aspects
- KH9 — closing the deal
- KH10 — staffing (recruiting, training, rewarding, rotating)
- KH11 — managing alliance-parent company relations
- KH12 — building trust with partner
- KH13 — conflict resolutions
- KH14 — renegotiating initial agreements with partner
- KH15 — logistics and resource transfer
- KH16 — cross-cultural training
- KH17 — knowledge/skills acquisition
- KH18 — knowledge/skills safeguarding
- KH19 — profit or capital repatriation
- KH20 — exiting from the alliance

Source: Simonin (1999).

Items Measuring Outsourcing Benefits

Business benefits Organizational benefits

- BUSB1 — allows focusing on core activities ORGB1 — allows access to latest technologies
- BUSB2 — produces cost savings ORGB2 — increases innovations trends
- BUSB3 — transfers fixed cost to variable ORGB3 — shortens activities development cycles
- BUSB4 — increases business flexibility ORGB4 — reduces organizational risks
- BUSB5 — allows to focus on internal business improvement ORGB5 — improves technologically operations
- BUSB6 — improves strategic positioning ORGB6 — reduces training costs
- BUSB7 — reduces capital expenditures ORGB7 — improves management processes
- BUSB8 — gets rid of problem functions ORGB8 — builds entry barriers for competitors

Source: Adapted from Ehie (2001) and Kremic et al. (2006).

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